

Enhancing Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution: Defect Engineering in MIL-101 (Cr) through 4- amiobenzoic acid Modification

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Abstract

Photocatalytic hydrogen production offers a promising route toward sustainable energy generation. Investigating the impact of defect engineering on the photocatalytic performance of MIL-101 (Cr), PABA was incorporated during synthesis. Characterization of the structural, morphological, and optical properties of both pristine and defective MIL-101 (Cr) was conducted using techniques such as XRD, SEM, FTIR, BET surface area analysis and TGA. The introduction of defects led to decreased crystallinity, increased pore size, and enhanced light absorption. Consequently, the defective MIL-101 (Cr) exhibited superior photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance compared to the pristine material, attributed to improved charge separation and a higher number of active sites. These findings underscore the potential of defect engineering as an effective strategy to enhance MOF-based photocatalysts for hydrogen production.

Key words: Photocatalysis, Hydrogen Evolution, Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs), MIL-101-Cr, Defect Engineering.

1. Introduction

The global pursuit of sustainable and clean energy sources has intensified research into hydrogen production as a viable alternative to fossil fuels [1]. Among various hydrogen generation methods, photocatalytic water splitting has emerged as a promising and environmentally friendly approach, utilizing solar energy to produce hydrogen with minimal carbon emissions [2]. However, the development of efficient and cost-effective photocatalysts remains a significant challenge [3][4].

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) have garnered attention in this regard due to their unique structural tunability [5], high porosity [6], and ability to facilitate light absorption and charge transport [7][8]. Among MOFs, MIL-101 (Cr) has demonstrated considerable potential as a photocatalyst owing to its stability, tunable band gap, and large surface area [9][10][11][12].

Defect engineering is essential for improving the performance of MOFs by modifying their structure to enhance electronic properties, porosity, and catalytic activity [13][6][14]. In photocatalytic hydrogen evolution, defects boost charge separation [15], reduce recombination, and create additional active sites, leading to improved efficiency [15][16][17]. They also optimize light absorption and band gap tuning, enabling better utilization of visible light for enhanced photocatalytic performance [14][18].

In this study, we conduct a comprehensive comparison between pristine MIL-101 (Cr) and defective MIL-101 (Cr) modified with 4-aminobenzoic acid (PABA) to evaluate their photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance. By investigating their structural characteristics, optical behavior, and hydrogen evolution rates, we aim to understand the role of PABA-induced defects in enhancing the photocatalytic activity of MIL-101 (Cr). The insights gained from this research will contribute to the development of more efficient MOF-based photocatalysts, paving the way for advanced materials in sustainable hydrogen production.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

All chemicals used in this study were of analytical reagent (AR) grade and utilized without further purification. The materials employed include chromium(III) nitrate nonahydrate ($\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Sigma Aldrich, 98%), ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$) (E. Merck Inc., 99%), methanol (CH_3OH) (E. Merck Inc., 99%), 1,4-benzenedicarboxylic acid (BDC) (Merck, 98%), PABA (Sigma Aldrich, 99%), deionized water (DI) for reactions and washing, N,N'-dimethylformamide (DMF) (Fluka Co., 99%), benzoic acid (Sigma Aldrich, 99%), acetone ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{O}$) (Sigma Aldrich, 99.5%).

2.2. Synthesis of MIL-101-Cr

A mixture of 0.8 grams of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.328 grams (2 mmol) of BDC was prepared. To this, 1.5 mL of 36% acetic acid and 10 mL of water were added. The resulting solution was then transferred to a Teflon-lined autoclave, which was placed inside a furnace. The furnace was set to heat at a rate of 22°C per hour until reaching 200°C , after which it was gradually cooled back to room temperature following the same heating program. The synthesized compound was purified by washing three times with DMF and subsequently sonicating it in ethanol for 1 hour. For activation, the material underwent a solvent exchange process, initially with methanol for 2 hours, followed by acetone for 24 hours. After air drying, the compound was further activated in a vacuum oven at 120°C for 16 hours. Finally, the resulting MOF was collected [19].

2.3. Synthesis of Defective MIL-101 (Cr) Structure Using PABA

A combination of 1.2 grams (3 mmol) of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.498 grams (3 mmol) of PABA, and 0.363 grams (3 mmol) of benzoic acid was prepared, followed by the addition of 15 mL of water. The mixture was then placed into a Teflon-lined autoclave, which was positioned inside a furnace and heated at a controlled rate of 22°C per hour until reaching 220°C . Once the target temperature was attained, the system was gradually cooled back to room temperature using the same programmed rate. To purify the synthesized material, it was washed three times with DMF and subsequently subjected to sonication in ethanol for 1 hour. The activation process involved an initial solvent exchange with methanol for 2 hours, followed by an extended solvent exchange with acetone for 24 hours. After air-drying at ambient temperature, the compound was further activated by placing it in a vacuum oven at 120°C for 16 hours. Finally, the resulting MOF was collected.

3. Characterization Techniques and procedure

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed using a Siemens 5000d diffractometer operating at 40 kV, with $\text{K}\alpha\text{-Co}$ and $\text{K}\alpha\text{-Cu}$ radiation, utilizing the Xpert Philips model. This technique was used to examine the crystalline structure and phase purity of the photocatalysts. The morphology and structural characteristics of the synthesized photocatalysts were further investigated through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with a CamScan MV2300, in conjunction with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDAX) using a JEOL Centurio spectrometer. This method provided insights into surface features and elemental composition. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) spectra were recorded using a Rad Bio 7FTS spectrophotometer in KBr pellet form to identify functional groups and confirm the formation of specific chemical bonds. The surface area and porosity of the samples were determined through nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms, employing the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method with a Micromeritics ASAP 2460 instrument, which is crucial for evaluating catalytic performance. The thermal stability and activation behavior of the samples were

assessed via thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a TA SDT650 analyzer, which measured decomposition temperatures and thermal resistance.

To investigate and compare the photocatalytic activity of the synthesized defective and non-defective samples, a hydrogen production test was conducted. The equipment and conditions used for the test included a cylindrical Pyrex reactor, which was air-cooled using a rotating system. A 100-watt xenon (Xe) lamp was employed as the photoreactor and light source for photocatalytic hydrogen production under visible light. High-lifetime arc lamps with ultraviolet to near-infrared light output and minimal light fluctuations were used in high-power xenon light sources. To measure the light intensity on the reactor, a light source was placed 10 cm away. In this photocatalytic experiment, 50 mg of the photocatalyst was dispersed in a 200 mL aqueous solution without any sacrificial agent.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. XRD

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern reveals a significant difference in crystallinity between MIL-101(Cr) and defective MIL-101(Cr) (D-MIL-101 (Cr)). The pristine MIL-101(Cr) exhibits sharp, well-defined peaks, indicating a highly crystalline structure with long-range periodicity. In contrast, the D-MIL-101 (Cr) shows a substantial reduction in peak intensity and noticeable broadening, suggesting a loss of crystallinity due to structural defects (Figure 1). The main peaks observed at 8.53° , 9.13° , and 16.59° are present in both samples, confirming that the fundamental MIL-101(Cr) framework remains intact [20]. However, in the defective sample, these peaks exhibit lower intensity and broadening, indicating increased disorder, likely due to missing linkers or framework distortions. It is important to highlight that the D-MIL-101-Cr sample lacks the diffraction peak at approximately 3.37° and 5.23° , which is present in MIL-101(Cr). This absence indicates that the structural modification with PABA may have disrupted certain crystallographic planes in the framework. These changes suggest that defect engineering has introduced structural irregularities, reducing the material's overall crystallinity and potentially altering its properties. Moreover, the diffraction patterns

observed at lower 2θ values indicate the porous characteristics of the MIL-101 (Cr) framework [21].

Figure 1- XRD patterns of MIL-101 (Cr) and D-MIL-101 (Cr).

4.2. SEM & EDS

The SEM analysis of MIL-101(Cr) and D-MIL-101(Cr) revealed significant differences in morphology and particle characteristics. Pristine MIL-101(Cr) exhibited well-defined octahedral crystals with smooth surfaces and uniform particle sizes ranging from approximately 500 nm to 1 μ m, consistent with its high crystallinity observed in XRD. In contrast, D-MIL-101(Cr) displayed larger particle sizes, suggesting that defect engineering and PABA modification influenced crystal growth. Despite being larger, the defective particles had irregular and distorted octahedral shapes, rougher surfaces, indicating structural disruptions (Figure 2 a-b). Additionally, some particles appeared aggregated or fractured, further confirming the loss of crystallinity seen in the XRD pattern. Overall, the SEM results complemented the XRD findings, demonstrating how defect engineering altered both the size and morphology of MIL-101(Cr) [21].

The EDAX analysis was conducted to assess the elemental composition of MIL-101-Cr and its defective variant. As illustrated in Figure 2 c-k, the resulting spectra confirmed that carbon (C), oxygen (O), and chromium (Cr) are the main elements present in both samples. Notably,

the analysis revealed distinct variations in elemental content, attributed to the incorporation of PABA in the defective MIL-101-Cr sample.

Figure 2- SEM images of (a) MIL-101 (Cr) and (b) D-MIL-101-Cr. EDAX images of (c-f) MIL-101 (Cr) and (g-k) D-MIL-101 (Cr).

4.3. FTIR

The FTIR spectrum presented in Figure 3 shows that the peak at $1,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to free PABA, while the peak at $1,508\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to C=C stretching vibrations, and the peak near $1,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is related to the symmetric stretching of C–O–C. Moreover, the peak around 570 cm^{-1} is linked to the Cr–O vibration, confirming the presence of a metal-organic framework structure. A comparison of the activated and non-activated MIL-101(Cr) samples demonstrates that after activation, the $1,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ peak vanishes, confirming the successful removal of free PABA during the activation process [22]. Additionally, the FTIR spectra of the defective MIL-101(Cr)-ABA compound show no major differences when compared to the

pristine MIL-101(Cr), suggesting that the introduction of defects did not alter the functional groups or chemical structure, implying that the PABA modification did not disrupt the core bonding environment within the framework.

Figure 3- FTIR spectra of non-activated and activated MIL-101 (Cr) and D-MIL-101 (Cr).

4.4. BET

The porosity characteristics of the materials were assessed through nitrogen adsorption measurements conducted at 77 K. As illustrated in Figure 4a, the pristine MIL-101 (Cr) sample exhibited a Type II isotherm, whereas the defective variant modified with benzoic acid followed a Type III pattern. BET surface area calculations showed a significant contrast, with MIL-101 (Cr) reaching 948.91 m²/g, while the defective sample experienced a considerable decline to 731.86 m²/g. This reduction is attributed to the expected removal of linkers during defect formation. Additionally, pore size analysis indicated an increase from 31.66 Å in MIL-101 (Cr) to 41.70 Å in the defective material, further confirming the structural changes induced by defect engineering [22]. As depicted in Figure 4b, these alterations emphasize the role of PABA in modifying the framework, leading to a decrease in surface area and an expansion in pore volume, aligning with the disruption of structural linkages and defect incorporation.

Figure 4- BET plots of (a) MIL-101 (Cr) and (b) D-MIL-101 (Cr).

4.5. TGA

TGA and derivative thermogravimetric analysis (DTGA) of defective MIL-101-Cr, both in its activated and non-activated forms, reveal the significant impact of activation on its thermal stability. Figure 5a-b presents the TGA and DTGA profiles for both samples, offering a comparative insight into their thermal behavior. During the initial heating phase (30–90°C), both samples undergo weight loss due to the evaporation of physically adsorbed water. The activated sample exhibits a smaller weight reduction, as seen in Figure 5a, indicating the successful removal of residual solvents through the activation process. Between 90–400°C, both materials display relative stability, with the activated defective MIL-101 (Cr) showing improved thermal resistance. This enhancement is attributed to the elimination of OH/F groups and structural refinement [23]. In the 400–520°C range, a pronounced weight loss occurs, corresponding to the decomposition of the organic linker (PABA) and the subsequent breakdown of the framework. Figure 5a illustrates that for defective MIL-101-Cr, this degradation begins at approximately 200°C, whereas in its activated form, the process is delayed until around 450°C. This shift highlights the greater structural integrity of the activated material. By 520°C, both samples stabilize with the formation of Cr₂O₃ residue, maintaining a residual weight of about 73% [21]. DTGA analysis (Figure 5b) further supports these findings, showing that activated defective MIL-101 (Cr) exhibits reduced weight loss at lower and mid-temperature ranges and demonstrates greater resistance to structural collapse. The DTGA peaks suggest the presence of unstable chemical species in defective MIL-101 (Cr), while the activated counterpart displays a more refined and stable framework due to the effective removal of these unstable groups [24].

Figure 5- TGA and (b) DTG plots of non-defective and defective MIL-101 (Cr).

4.6. Photocatalytic hydrogen evolution

As shown in Figure 6, the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance of MIL-101 (Cr) and D-MIL-101 (Cr) modified with PABA was evaluated under visible light irradiation, revealing distinct differences between the two materials. The introduction of PABA-induced defects significantly influenced the photocatalytic activity. The D-MIL-101 (Cr) exhibited a hydrogen evolution rate of $449 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$, which was notably higher than that of pristine MIL-101-Cr, which achieved only $181 \mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$. This improvement can be attributed to the presence of structural defects that act as active sites, facilitating better charge carrier mobility and reducing recombination rates. Additionally, the modified MIL-101 (Cr) demonstrated enhanced light absorption in the visible region, further contributing to its superior photocatalytic performance. These findings suggest that defect engineering through PABA modification is an effective strategy for improving the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution capabilities of MIL-101-Cr.

Figure 6- Comparison of Hydrogen evolution rate of MIL-101 (Cr) and D-MIL-101 (CR).

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrated that introducing structural defects in MIL-101 (Cr) through PABA modification significantly enhances its photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance. The D-MIL-101-Cr exhibited increased porosity, altered crystallinity, and improved light absorption, leading to superior hydrogen generation efficiency under visible light irradiation. The defect sites facilitated enhanced charge separation, reducing recombination rates and boosting catalytic activity. These results underscore the potential of defect-engineered MOFs for sustainable hydrogen production, paving the way for further advancements in photocatalyst design and application.

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